

FACTORS AFFECTING OFFLINE & ONLINE SHOPPING BEHAVIOR OF RESPONDENTS: AN EMPIRICAL STUDY OF PUNE CITY

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ABSTRACT

Although the use of online modes for shopping has increased at phenomenal pace, still only 25% of market is penetrated with online stores, as a result a large number of people are still relying on traditional methods. Thus, there is a need to study those factors, which are resisting people to shop online. In fast expanding market, virtual marketplace practitioners are facing issues to understand the mechanisms of virtual shopping and the behaviour of the online consumer. The objective of this paper is to study the factors affecting online & offline shopping behaviour of Consumers. It has been concluded that there is a significant difference between the factors affecting online and offline shopping behaviour.

Keywords: Offline Shopping, Online Shopping, Shopping Behavior

INTRODUCTION:

In current marketing scenario, the learning of consumer buying behaviour is vital. Without consumers, no business association can survive. The market is totally consumer driven. All business activities are targeted towards the consumers and consumer satisfaction. Consumer behaviour study is based on consumer buying behaviour, with the customer having three discrete roles of client, spender and purchaser. The study of consumer behaviour focuses on how individuals make decisions to spend their available resources (time, money, effort) on consumption-related items. The internet is being developed rapidly since last two decades, and with relevant digital economy that is driven by information technology also being build up worldwide. Internet is helping in promotion of products in better way and online advertisements are quite effective. Therefore detailed product information and improved services over web has attracted people to rely more on online services instead of traditional methods. However, online market has risen from last decade but still traditional methods of purchasing are more acceptable than online or through web. Only 25% of market is penetrated with online stores, as a result a large number of people are still relying on traditional methods. Therefore the study is important in this regard.

LITERATURE REVIEW:

According to **Hult, G. T. M., Sharma, P. N., Morgeson III, F. V., & Zhang, Y. (2019)** “Retailers seek to utilize both online and offline purchase channels strategically to satisfy customers and thrive in the marketplace. Unfortunately, current multichannel research is deficient in answering what drives customers’ satisfaction, and consequently their loyalty, differently when customers purchase online versus at a physical store. This gap in knowledge can be a significant concern for retailers due to the negative impact of having dissatisfied customers on their bottom lines. Using a version of the American Customer Satisfaction Index (ACSI) model, this paper demonstrate several important purchase-channel differences in the antecedents of customer satisfaction and its subsequent effect on customer loyalty. Specifically, authors show that when retail customers buy electronic goods online they view purchase value as a significant attribute in rating satisfaction, and are more satisfaction-sensitive when making repurchase decisions than when they purchase offline. On the other hand, the overall quality of the purchase experience and customer expectations are stronger drivers of customer satisfaction in the offline purchases. Authors provide evidence that these differences between the channels generally persist across customer demographics (gender, age, and education) and broader product categories, and we also discuss the specific contexts where they do not.”

Heejin Lim and Alan F. Dubinsky (2018) analyzed “an expectancy value approach to study consumers’ perception of e-shopping characteristics with reference to e-store factors viz., merchandise; convenience, interactivity; reliability; promotions, and navigation. The findings obtained demonstrated that consumers’ attitude toward online shopping was positively related to their perceptions of Website merchandise and reliability attributes.”

Pavlou(2017) evaluated “online transactions that can be considered to consist of three key steps such as information retrieval; information transfer, and product purchase. The information retrieval and exchange steps are regarded as intentions to use a website; however, product purchase is more applicable to an intention to transact with a website. Purchase intention has been defined as the situation which manifests itself when a consumer is willing and intends to become involved in online transactions. Online transactions have three different characteristics from traditional transactions viz., Interactions use extensive technology; second the uncertain, temporal, impersonal character of the online transaction environment and third, Open, unpredictable, and technological infrastructures during the processes of online transactions”

Lopes & Tanaya (2016) in their study stated that Consumers are very particular about their products purchase irrespective of online or offline purchase. The eyewear industry has grown tremendously in India. The consumer preference is also changing as people now prefer to shop online rather than offline shopping for eyewear products. The factors such as awareness, willingness, average monthly spend on eyewear, preference amongst others are prominent factors considered while offline and online shopping of eyewear products.

Singhal & Shekhawat (2015) in their study did an extensive review of literature that has lead to the extraction of various factors affecting online purchasing of various products and services. The most motivating factors have been identified which encourage consumers to shop online. The study also

unveils the various resisting factors, which act as barrier and divert the consumers towards traditional buying mechanism.

Riquelme, Isabel P., and Sergio Román,(2014) examined the role of several consumers' cognitive and psychographic traits in their perceptions of retailers' deceptive practices (perceived deception) and the different effects on perceived deception associated with online vis-à-vis in-store shopping.

OBJECTIVE:

The purposes of this research paper is to study the factors affecting online & offline shopping behaviour of Consumers

Hypothesis:

H₀: There is no significant difference between the factors affecting online and offline shopping behaviour

H₁: There is a significant difference between the factors affecting online and offline shopping behaviour

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

(a) Research Design: - To have a better understanding about the issue descriptive research design was used. To get the primary data close ended questionnaire was administrated.

(b) Sample Design: - 300 respondents were selected through stratified purposive sampling.

(c) Analysis: - The data collected was analyzed with the help of Arithmetic mean and t-test.

ANALYSIS & INTERPRETATIONS

Respondents were asked to indicate factors influence them for shopping on 5 point scale ranging from 5 (Extremely Influential) to 1 (Not at all Influential). Final ranking is obtained with the help of arithmetic mean. The analysis of results is presented in further sub sections.

1. Factors affecting Offline Shopping behavior of Respondents

The table 1 shows that, the Extremely Influential factor during offline shopping was Reliability of Manufacturers with a mean score of 4.22. The factors ranked from 2nd to 4th and Very much influence the offline shopping were After Sales Service (Mean Score = 3.91), Product Description (Mean Score = 3.55) and Store Ambiance (Mean Score = 3.55) respectively. Mean score analysis revealed that factors which somewhat influence the online shopping behavior of respondents and ranked from 5th to 13th positions were Competitive Pricing (Mean Score = 3.28), Schemes & Offers (Mean Score = 3.25), Availability of Variety and brand of Products (Mean Score = 3.16), Product Return facility (Mean Score = 3.09), More

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Relaxing Shopping (Mean Score = 2.99), Saves Money (Mean Score = 2.8), Saves Time (Mean Score = 2.78), Convenient Delivery (Mean Score = 2.71), and Cash on Delivery facility (Mean Score = 2.66).

Table 1: Factors affecting Offline Shopping behavior of Respondents

S. No.	Factors	Mean Score	Rank	Level of Influence
1	Reliability of Manufacturers	4.22	1	Extremely Influential
2	After Sales Service	3.91	2	Very Influential
3	Product Description	3.55	3	Very Influential
4	Store Ambiance	3.42	4	Very Influential
5	Competitive Pricing	3.28	5	Somewhat Influential
6	Schemes & Offers	3.25	6	Somewhat Influential
7	Availability of Variety and brand of Products	3.16	7	Somewhat Influential
8	Product Return facility	3.09	8	Somewhat Influential
9	More Relaxing Shopping	2.99	9	Somewhat Influential
10	Saves Money	2.8	10	Somewhat Influential
11	Saves Time	2.78	11	Somewhat Influential
12	Convenient Delivery	2.71	12	Somewhat Influential
13	Cash on Delivery facility	2.66	13	Somewhat Influential

2. Factors affecting Online Shopping behavior of Respondents

Similarly respondents were asked to indicate the influence of the factors affecting their online shopping decision on five point scale starting from extremely influential (5) to not at all influential (1). The table 2 shows that, the “Availability of Variety and brand of Products” was the most influencing factor affecting the respondents’ decision of online shopping with a mean score of 4.65 followed by Schemes & Offers (Weighted Mean score = 4.63). Convenient Delivery ranked 3rd with a Mean score of 4.46, followed by Competitive Pricing that ranked 4th with a weighted mean score of 4.44. Saves Time was the fifth influencing factor of online shopping with mean score of 4.40 tailed by Product Return facility at 6th rank with a weighted mean score of 4.36.

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Saves Money graded at 7th place with a mean score of 4.26, trailed by More Relaxing Shopping at 8th rank with a mean score of 4.15. 24 X 7 Shopping facility ranked as 9th influencing factor affecting respondents' decision of online shopping with a mean score of 4.07. The mean score of Website Design was 3.91 and ranked at 10th place followed by Product Description (rank=11) with a weighted mean score of 3.84.

The last four ranked factor affecting the online shopping behavior of respondents were After Sales Service (Mean Score=3.75), Customer Care Facility (Mean Score=3.73), Cash on Delivery facility (Mean Score=3.65) and Reliability of Manufacturers (Mean Score=3.47).

Table 2: Factors affecting Online Shopping behavior of Respondents

S. No.	Factors	Mean Score	Rank	Level of Influence
1	Availability of Variety and brand of Products	4.65	1	Extremely Influential
2	Schemes & Offers	4.63	2	Extremely Influential
3	Convenient Delivery	4.46	3	Extremely Influential
4	Competitive Pricing	4.44	4	Extremely Influential
5	Saves Time	4.4	5	Extremely Influential
6	Product Return facility	4.36	6	Extremely Influential
7	Saves Money	4.26	7	Extremely Influential
8	More Relaxing Shopping	4.15	8	Very Influential
9	24 X 7 Shopping facility	4.07	9	Very Influential
10	Website Design	3.91	10	Very Influential
11	Product Description	3.84	11	Very Influential
12	After Sales Service	3.75	12	Very Influential
13	Customer Care Facility	3.73	13	Very Influential
14	Cash on Delivery facility	3.65	14	Very Influential
15	Reliability of Manufacturers	3.47	15	Very Influential

3. Hypothesis Testing

H₀: There is no significant difference between the factors affecting online and offline shopping behaviour

H₁: There is a significant difference between the factors affecting online and offline shopping behaviour

t- test was used to measure the significant difference between the factors affecting online and offline shopping behaviour. The table 3 is presenting the results of t-test.

Table 3: t-test Results to Measure significant difference between the factors affecting online and offline shopping behaviour

Factor	Type of Shopping	Mean	S.D.	t-value	p-value	Result
Saves Time	Offline	2.78	1.172	17.029	0.00	Significant
	Online	4.4	1.103			
Saves Money	Offline	2.8	0.988	17.445	0.00	Significant
	Online	4.26	1.018			
More Relaxing Shopping	Offline	2.99	1.28	11.695	0.00	Significant
	Online	4.15	1.063			
Convenient Delivery	Offline	2.78	1.336	18.004	0.00	Significant
	Online	4.46	0.834			
Reliability of Manufacturers	Offline	4.22	0.852	7.783	0.00	Significant
	Online	3.47	1.371			
Availability of Variety and brand of Products	Offline	3.16	1.276	16.485	0.00	Significant
	Online	4.65	0.842			
Schemes & Offers	Offline	3.25	1.378	14.835	0.00	Significant
	Online	4.63	0.728			
Cash on Delivery facility	Offline	2.66	1.542	7.704	0.00	Significant

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	Online	3.65	1.505			
Competitive Pricing	Offline	3.28	1.361	12.477	0.00	Significant
	Online	4.44	0.795			
Product Return facility	Offline	3.09	1.672	11.671	0.00	Significant
	Online	4.36	0.82			
Product Description	Offline	3.55	1.259	3.129	0.00	Significant
	Online	3.84	0.945			
After Sales Service	Offline	3.91	1.338	1.631	0.104	Significant
	Online	3.75	0.979			

Level of Significance = 5%

It can be observed that all the t-values are significant which leads to the rejection of hypothesis so it can be concluded that there is a significant difference between the factors affecting online and offline shopping behaviour

CONCLUSION:

From this research following conclusions can be drawn:-

1. The Extremely Influential factor during offline shopping was Reliability of Manufacturers followed by After Sales Service.
2. Availability of Variety and brand of Products was the most influencing factor affecting the respondents' decision of online shopping followed by Schemes & Offers.
3. There is a significant difference between the factors affecting online and offline shopping behaviour

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